

End-to-end error control coding capability of NB-IoT transmissions in a GEO satellite system with time-packed optical feeder link^{*}

Joan Bas¹ and Alexis A. Dowhuszko²

¹ Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Castelldefels, Spain

Email: joan.bas@cttc.es

<http://www.cttc.es/people/jbas/>

² Department of Communications and Networking, Aalto University, Finland

Email: joan.bas@cttc.es; alexis.dowhuszko@aalto.fi

<https://research.aalto.fi/en/persons/alexis-dowhuszko>

Abstract. This paper focuses on the return link of a GEO satellite system that collects information from a large number of IoT devices that are sparsely distributed in a large geographical area. Narrow-Band (NB) IoT transmissions, with suitable Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), are Detected-and-Forwarded onboard the satellite, mapping each QAM symbol of the radio access link (uplink) into another equivalent PAM symbol that is suitable to modulate the intensity of the optical feeder link (downlink). Given the very large number of IoT devices that is expected to be served by the GEO satellite system, the feeder link (downlink) of the return channel is expected to be bottleneck. To tackle this limitation, apart from using an optical feeder link, time-packing is proposed to reduce the transmission time of the feeder link (downlink) without increasing the signal bandwidth and augment the number of IoT devices that could be simultaneously served in the radio access links (uplink). The Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) that the time-packed feeder link generates is mitigated in part at the satellite gateway, using for this purpose an adaptive linear equalizer. After optical-to-electrical conversion, the NB-IoT codewords that are received in the gateway are decoded, correcting simultaneously errors introduced in both radio access and optical feeder links. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the error correction capability that the MCS of NB-IoT has when used to protect the hybrid radio/optical end-to-end return link, particularly when using a large overlapping factor to increase the optical feeder link data rate.

Keywords: High-Throughput Satellite · Optical feeder link · Narrow-Band IoT · Return channel · Time-Packing · Modulation and Coding.

^{*} This work has received funding from the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities under project TERESA-TEC2017-90093-C3-1-R (AEI/FEDER,UE) and from the Catalan Government under grants 2017-SGR-891 and 2017-SGR-1479.

1 Introduction

The increase of the spectral efficiency is a key challenge to meet the demand for higher capacity wireless links in future communication systems. This fact becomes critical in satellite communications and IoT systems, where the link propagation delay is large and the modulation orders that are available for communication are low. In this regard, the so-called Faster-Than-Nyquist (FTN) transmission technique, which is also known as time-packing and was proposed by Mazo in the 1970s [?], has been revisited nowadays for increasing the spectral efficiency of Beyond 5G [?]. As a side-effect, time-packing can also provide some additional PHY-layer security feature by adjusting the temporal separation between consecutive pulse-shapes, making that only the authorized user is able to detect the transmitted symbol stream with low enough Bit Error Rate (BER) [?].

The combination of increased spectral efficiency (without bandwidth expansion) and additional PHY-layer security features provides an interesting combination that fuels the commercial success IoT-based services. According to Northern Sky Research reports, telemetry applications have the largest share (28 %) when measuring the services with highest economic impact in IoT technology nowadays, followed by Telematics/Analytics applications (13 %) and Asset Tracking services (11 %), respectively [?, ?]. At this point, it is important to highlight that the three previously listed IoT applications require in general Narrow-Band (NB) requirements and high levels of security. Therefore, time-packing is a good candidate solution to fulfill these two IoT requirements when relying on satellite communication systems with extremely large coverage area.

The use of time-packing techniques reduces the temporal duration of the IoT frames, which is beneficial for increasing the amount of traffic that can be simultaneously collected in the radio access links (enabled by multiple spot beams), and aggregate it together in the point-to-point optical feeder link of the GEO satellite system. However, the implementation of time-packing techniques also have some challenges. For example, when packing more densely adjacent data-carrying pulses, the Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) of the resulting time-domain signal increases, reducing the end-to-end spectral efficiency as certain blocks of the transmission chain – such as the radio power amplifiers and the external optical Match-Zehnder Modulators (MZM) – have a linear response only on a limited input signal range. It is important to highlight that the PAPR of the time-packed waveform does not depend only on the selected overlapping factor, but also on the on the roll-off factor of the Square-Root Raised-Cosine (SRRC) pulse-shaping filter that is used [?].

Finally, when focusing on the received signal processing at the satellite gateway, we note that large overlapping and/or low roll-off factors of the time-packed waveform introduce notable Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI). This means that it is very difficult to implement a Maximum Likelihood Sequence Detector (MLSD) or Viterbi Equalizer, particularly when the modulation order of the data-carrying signal is large. Therefore, sub-optimal adaptive linear equalizers can be used to remove most of the ISI that time-packing introduces and, after that, a low-complexity symbol-by-symbol detectors can be implemented. In this paper, we

aim at characterizing the end-to-end error control correction capabilities that Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) of NB-IoT transmissions can provide when concatenating the radio access link with the optical feeder link of a GEO satellite system. Note that the use of end-to-end encoding makes sense in low-complexity satellite systems, as no additional error control coding can be added onboard the satellite to protect the end-to-end transmission against the error introduced in the optical feeder link. This is the reason by the Detection-and-Forward architecture has been proposed to forward the information, where only the hard-detection of the M -QAM symbols (access link) and its mapping into equivalent M -PAM symbols (feeder link) is performed in the GEO satellite node.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the system model, including details of the NB-IoT transmission on the radio access link and the generation of the time-packed signal that is used to modulate the intensity of the optical feeder link. Section 3 explains the adaptive linear equalization approach that is used to mitigate the ISI that time-packing generates in the feeder link, whereas Section 4 presents the simulation setup and the performance evaluation when different MCS of NB-IoT are used to control the errors introduced in the whole reverse link (end-to-end). Finally, Section 5 draws the conclusions.

2 System Model

The block diagram of the proposed High-Throughput Satellite (HTS) system is illustrated in Fig. 1. It consists of a large number of sparsely deployed IoT devices, which use the Geosynchronous Equatorial Orbit (GEO) satellite as Detect-and-Forward relaying node to reach the remote satellite gateway. Different wireless communication technologies are used for the access link (uplink) and feeder link (downlink), namely radio and optical wireless, respectively.

The radio waveform that the IoT terminals generate for the uplink transmission follows the NB-IoT format. In the satellite, the M -QAM symbols that are received in uplink are first detected and then mapped into points of an M -PAM constellation, to make them suitable to modulate in intensity the light beam that the laser diode onboard the satellite emits in downlink. When performing this electrical-to-optical conversion, time-packing feature is added in the M -PAM downlink transmission in order to reduce the symbol time and increase the number of IoT terminals that can be simultaneously served in the access spot beams. In the next sections, the signal model for each link is explained in further detail.

2.1 NB-IoT transmission in radio access (uplink of reverse link)

The NB-IoT communication in the reverse link, which starts in the IoT devices and ends in the satellite Gateway, consist of the following physical channels [?], [?], [?]:

- Narrowband Physical Uplink Shared Channel (NPUSCH), which is used to transmit uplink transport block on the orthogonal Resource Units (RUs) that the target IoT device has received.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of a GEO satellite system that implements time-packing in the optical feeder link to increase the number of NB-IoT devices that can be served. The GEO satellite implements a Detection-and-Forward strategy, adapting the M-QAM symbols of the radio access link to the M-PAM symbols that modulate in intensity the laser diode. The coding scheme that the NB-IoT devices select is used to correct errors introduced in both radio access and optical feeder parts of the return link.

- Narrow Band Physical Random Access Channels (NPRACH), which enables the random access procedure among the IoT devices that have information to transmit in the shared radio access link.

Table 1: Details of the Resource Units (RU) and Uplink slots for each NPUSCH's format and different subcarrier separations (see Table 10.1.2.3-1 of [?])

NPUSCH format	Δf	N_{sc}^{RU}	N_{slots}^{UL}	N_{syms}^{UL}
1	3.75 kHz	1	16	7
		1	16	
	15 kHz	3	8	
		6	4	
		12	2	
2	3.75 kHz	1	4	
	15 kHz	1	4	

From both channels, this paper focused on the NPUSCH, and assumes that the random access procedure has been successfully performed, such that the IoT devices know the orthogonal RUs that they can use for uplink communication. The NPUSCH is based on the following parts: 24 bits of Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC), Turbo channel encoding with a mother code of 1/3, rate matching, physical-layer Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ), scrambling, modulations of $\pi/2$ -BPSK and $\pi/4$ -QPSK for single-tone transmissions, and QPSK for multi-tone transmissions. Moreover, the NPUSCH has two formats: Format 1 is

used for data transmissions on the Uplink Shared Channel (UL-SCH), whereas Format 2 is used for Uplink Control Information (UCI), such as ACK/NACK transmissions of the HARQ mechanism. The uplink transmission can support two different subcarrier separations (Δf). When $\Delta f = 15$ kHz, 12 consecutive sub-carriers are allocated for uplink transmission using time slots with duration of 0.5 ms. On the other hand, when $\Delta f = 3.75$ kHz, 48 consecutive sub-carriers are allocated for uplink transmission in time slots of duration 2 ms. The distribution of the number of resource units (N_{sc}^{RU}) and number of slots (N_{slots}^{UL}) for the different formats of the NPUSCH is provided in Table 1 (See Table 10.1.2.3-1 of [?]). The modulation scheme that is used depends on the number of RUs N_{sc}^{RU} , as illustrated in Table 2 (See Table 10.1.3.2-1 of [?]). From this table, we will focus on format 1 and single-subcarrier transmissions (*i.e.*, $N_{sc}^{RU} = 1$), since it enables the use of both BPSK and QPSK modulations.

Table 2: Supported modulation formats in NPUSCH (see Table 10.1.3.2-1 of [?]).

NPUSCH format	N_{sc}^{RU}	Modulation scheme
1	1	BPSK, QPSK
	>1	QPSK
2	1	BPSK

The following step consists in associating the modulation with the error control coding scheme, which will define the Transport Block Size (TBS) and the corresponding code rate. More precisely, the NPUSCH can support until 11 possible MCS, which are related with the modulation and TBS index as shown in Table 3 (See Table 16.5.1.2-1 of [?]). From these values, we observe that BPSK modulation is used only in the first two possible MCS indexes (*i.e.*, $I_{MCS} = 0, 1$), whereas in the others MCS indexes rely on QPSK modulation (*i.e.*, $I_{MCS} = 2, \dots, 10$). This table also relates the index of the MCS (I_{MCS}) with the index of the TBS (I_{TBS}). NB-IoT has multiple possible TBS values, which depend on the modulation and the code rate that is used in each case. Thus, from the point of view of I_{TBS} , the first and third MCS indexes utilize BPSK modulation, whereas the others utilize QPSK modulation. Then, in order to know the transport block size, Table 4 associates each TBS index (I_{TBS}) with the Resource Unit index (I_{RU}).

From Table 4, it is possible to observe that the minimum and maximum TBS for the NPUSCH is 16 and 2536 bits, respectively. We note that the different TBS may be associated with different modulation formats. For example, when BPSK modulation is used, the minimum and maximum TBS that is possible is 16 and 424 bits, respectively. On the other hand, when using QPSK modulation, the minimum and maximum TBS that is allowed is 24 and 2536 bits, respectively. Nonetheless, the code rate that is associated to each TBS is fixed, and depends on the I_{TBS} and the I_{RU} indexes that are used. More precisely, the code rate

Table 3: Modulation, TBS, and MCS mapping (see Table 16.5.1.2-1 of [?]).

MCS Index	Modulation Order	TBS Index
I_{MCS}	Q_m	I_{TBS}
0	1	0
1	1	2
2	2	1
3	2	3
4	2	4
5	2	5
6	2	6
7	2	7
8	2	8
9	2	9
10	2	10

that correspond to a given NB-IoT transmission in uplink is given by

$$R_c^{\text{UL}} = \frac{\text{TBS}}{N_{\text{RE}} N_{\text{RU}} N_b}, \quad (1)$$

where N_{RE} is the number of Resource Elements (RE) that are allocated per RU, N_{RU} is the number of RU utilized in each NB-IoT information block, and N_b is the number of bits that is transmitted in each resource element. Note that $N_{\text{RE}} = 96$ (144) for single-tone (multi-tone) transmission, whereas $N_b = 1$ (2) for BPSK (QPSK) modulation, respectively. In addition, Table 5 shows the number of RU utilized in each block as function of the RU index that is selected.

In our simulation setting, we keep fixed the TBS. Then, from Table 4, we obtain the different I_{TBS} and I_{RU} combinations that can be supported with the selected TBS. Each I_{RU} can be associated with the required number of resource units (N_{RU}) taking advantage of the Table 5. Note that when $N_{\text{RU}} = 1$, then we are in presence of a single-tone transmission where the number of resource elements is $N_{\text{RE}} = 96$. Otherwise, the transmission is multi-tone, and the number of resource elements is $N_{\text{RE}} = 144$. The index I_{TBS} that is obtained for the given TBS can be associated with the modulation order of the transmission (N_b) using Table 3. Finally, Table 6 shows the code rates that can be supported in a single-tone transmission. For instance, if we set the TBS size to 256 bits, then Table 6 shows the code rates that the NPUSCH format 1 can support when BPSK and QPSK modulation for different resource unit indexes (I_{RU}). So, from Table 7 we observe that if $\text{TBS} = 256$ and $N_b = 1$ (BPSK modulation), then it is only possible to use two different code rates: $R_c^{\text{UL}} = 0.27$ (with $I_{\text{RU}} = 9$) and $R_c^{\text{UL}} = 0.44$ (with $I_{\text{RU}} = 5$). On the contrary, for $\text{TBS} = 256$ and $N_b = 2$ (QPSK modulation), there are five possible code rates: $R_c^{\text{UL}} = 0.17, 0.27, 0.33, 0.44, 0.67$ (with $I_{\text{RU}} = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6$, respectively). Note that when $I_{\text{RU}} = 0$, there is no MCS that can be supported when $\text{TBS} = 256$ bits.

After the encoding and modulation, the uplink NB-IoT transmissions are based on Single-Carrier Frequency Division Multiplex Access (SC-FDMA), which can be implemented with a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) precoding before

Table 4: TBS in bits in terms of I_{TBS} and I_{RU} (see Table 16.5.1.2-2 of [?]).

I_{TBS}	I_{RU}							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
0	16	32	56	88	120	152	208	256
1	24	56	88	144	176	208	256	344
2	32	72	144	176	208	256	328	424
3	40	104	176	208	256	328	440	568
4	56	120	208	256	328	408	552	680
5	72	144	224	328	424	504	680	872
6	88	176	256	392	504	600	808	1000
7	104	224	328	472	584	712	1000	1224
8	120	256	392	536	680	808	1096	1384
9	136	296	456	616	776	936	1256	1544
10	144	328	504	680	872	1000	1384	1736
11	176	376	584	776	1000	1192	1608	2024
12	208	440	680	1000	1128	1352	1800	2280
13	224	488	744	1032	1256	1544	2024	2536

Table 5: Number of Resource Units (N_{RU}) that corresponds to the different Resource Unit indexes (I_{RU}) of the NPUSCH (see Table 16.5.1.1-2 of [?])

I_{RU}	N_{RU}
0	1
1	2
2	3
3	4
4	5
5	6
6	8
7	10

Table 6: Code rates for NPUSCH format 1 in terms of I_{TBS} and I_{RU} for a single single-tone transmission. The code rates R_c^{UL} are obtained from equation (1).

Modulation Order	I_{TBS}	Index of Resource Units I_{RU} (Single-Tone case)							
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0	0.17	0.17	0.19	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.27	0.27
1	2	0.33	0.38	0.50	0.46	0.43	0.44	0.43	0.44
2	1	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.19	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.18
2	3	0.21	0.27	0.31	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.30
2	4	0.29	0.31	0.36	0.33	0.34	0.35	0.36	0.35
2	5	0.38	0.38	0.39	0.43	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.45
2	6	0.46	0.46	0.44	0.51	0.53	0.52	0.53	0.52
2	7	0.54	0.58	0.57	0.61	0.61	0.62	0.65	0.64
2	8	0.63	0.67	0.68	0.70	0.71	0.70	0.71	0.72
2	9	0.71	0.77	0.79	0.80	0.81	0.81	0.82	0.80
2	10	0.75	0.85	0.88	0.89	0.91	0.87	0.90	0.90

Table 7: Code rates for NPUSCH format 1 in terms of I_{RU} for a single-tone transmission when the TBS is set to 256 bits.

Modulation	Index of Resource Units I_{RU} (Single-Tone case)							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BPSK	-	-	-	-	-	0.44	-	0.27
QPSK	-	0.67	0.44	0.33	0.27	-	0.17	-

Fig. 2: Return's link scheme from the IoT terminal to the satellite (with electrical-to-optical conversion), and from the satellite to the gateway (recovered IoT payload).

the uplink Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) block. After that, the signal is upconverted and transmitted to the satellite on a suitable Radio Frequency (RF) band. The SC-FDMA signal that is received in the satellite is then demodulated and re-mapped into M -PAM waveform, which is suitable to modulate the intensity of the laser diode of the optical feeder link in downlink. On the other side of optical wireless link, the satellite gateway performs the optical-to-electrical conversion with the aid of a photodetector (direct detection), where the payload of the IoT transmission is finally recovered after demodulation and decoding the received codeword. For a general overview of the different blocks that constitute the reverse link of the GEO satellite system, please refer to Fig. 2.

2.2 Optical transmission in feeder link (downlink of reverse channel)

The time-domain signal that a transmitter implementing time-packing strategy generates can be formulated as

$$s(t) = \sum_k s[k] g_{\text{tx}}(t - k(1 - \delta)T_s), \quad (2)$$

where k is the position of the data symbol in the input symbol stream $\{s[k]\}$, T_s represents the Nyquist symbol time, $g_{\text{tx}}(t)$ symbolizes the time response of the transmit pulse-shaping filter, and δ indicates the overlapping factor used for time-packing. The transmit pulses with response $g_{\text{tx}}(t)$ are designed to have unit energy and to be orthogonal when shifted by integer multiples of T_s . Nevertheless, when implementing time-packing, the orthogonality among adjacent pulses is lost as $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{tx}}(t)g_{\text{tx}}(t - n(1 - \delta)T_s)dt = 0$ only holds when there is no overlapping. Due to that, ISI is added in transmission when $\delta > 0$ but, in return, a higher signaling rate

$$R'_s = \frac{R_s}{(1 - \delta)} \geq R_s = \frac{1}{T_s} \quad (3)$$

can be achieved without increasing the communication bandwidth. Thanks to this approach, time-packing allows a more efficient use of the communication bandwidth at the expenses of adding ISI, which must be mitigated in reception.

The driving voltage of the external MZM that is placed onboard the satellite is given by

$$v_{\text{mzm}}(t) = V_B + \beta \tilde{s}(t) (V_\pi/\pi), \quad (4)$$

where V_B and V_π are the bias and half-wavelength voltages of the MZM, β is the intensity modulation index, and

$$\tilde{s}(t) = s(t)/\sqrt{\mathbb{E}\{|s(t)|^2\}}, \quad (5)$$

is the *normalized* continuous-time M -PAM signal. In the latter formula, $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$ represents the mathematical expectation of the corresponding time-domain signal. We note that the specific choice of β controls the range in which the MZM works. Deep intensity modulation indexes (*i.e.*, large β) increase the power on the optical feeder link sidebands but, at the same time, increment the non-linear distortion power on the electrical signal recovered in the satellite gateway.

The relation between the driving voltage $v_{\text{mzm}}(t)$ and the optical field at the MZM output $E_o(t)$ is given by [?]

$$E_o(t) = \cos \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{v_{\text{mzm}}(t)}{V_\pi} \right] \sqrt{2P_{\text{o,ld}}} \cos(\omega_o t), \quad (6)$$

where $P_{\text{o,ld}}$ is the mean optical power of the LD that feeds the MZM and ω_o is the angular frequency of the *unmodulated optical carrier* that is transmitted with

the *optical sidebands*. Then, the instantaneous value that the optical intensity modulated signal takes at the output of the MZM becomes

$$\begin{aligned} p_o(t) &= E_o^2(t) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{v_{\text{mzm}}(t)}{V_\pi}\right) 2P_{o,\text{ld}} \cos^2(\omega_o t), \\ &= \left[1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi V_B}{V_\pi} + \beta \tilde{s}(t)\right)\right] P_{o,\text{ld}} \cos^2(\omega_o t). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

When the quadrature bias point $V_B = (3V_\pi)/2$ is used,

$$p_o(t) = \left[1 + \sin\left(\beta \tilde{s}(t)\right)\right] P_{o,\text{ld}} \cos^2(\omega_o t) \approx \underbrace{[1 + \beta \tilde{s}(t)]}_{\text{modulating signal}} \underbrace{P_{o,\text{ld}} \cos^2(\omega_o t)}_{\text{optical carrier}} \quad \beta \ll 1, \quad (8)$$

where the latter approximation is due to $\sin(x) \approx x$ for $x \ll 1$. In this case, the impact of the MZM non-linear distortion can be neglected.

The Free Space Loss (FSL) in the optical feeder link is given by

$$L_{o,\text{fsl}} = \lambda^2 / (4\pi d_{\text{fso}})^2, \quad (9)$$

where d_{fso} is the link range and λ is the wavelength that the optical feeder link utilizes. Besides the FSL, an additional loss $L_{o,\text{atm}}$ is experienced when the optical signal propagates through the low layers of the atmosphere, particularly in case of bad weather conditions in which visibility is reduced.

The optical signal that reaches the PD generates an electrical current, *i.e.*,

$$i_D(t) = I_D + i_d(t) = \mu \frac{G_{o,\text{tx}} G_{o,\text{rx}} G_{o,\text{edfa}}}{L_{o,\text{fsl}} L_{o,\text{atm}} L_{o,\text{sys}}} \int_t^{t+T_o} p_o(\tau) d\tau, \quad (10)$$

$$\int_t^{t+T_o} p_o(\tau) d\tau = \frac{P_{o,\text{ld}}}{2} \left[1 + \sin\left(\beta \tilde{s}(t)\right)\right] \quad (11)$$

where $T_o = 2\pi/\omega_o$ is the period of the optical carrier, μ [A/W] is the PD responsivity, $G_{o,\text{tx}}$ and $G_{o,\text{rx}}$ are the optical gains of the transmit and receive telescopes, respectively, $G_{o,\text{edfa}}$ is the gain of the Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) placed before the PD in the satellite gateway, and $L_{o,\text{sys}}$ accounts the system losses in the optical feeder link. Note that the current in (10) can be divided into two terms, where the DC component is given by

$$I_D = \mathbb{E}\{i_D(t)\} = \mu \frac{G_{o,\text{tx}} G_{o,\text{rx}} G_{o,\text{edfa}}}{L_{o,\text{fsl}} L_{o,\text{atm}} L_{o,\text{sys}}} \frac{P_{o,\text{ld}}}{2}, \quad (12)$$

and remains fixed regardless of β , whereas the AC component depends on the intensity modulation index and attains the form

$$i_d(t) = i_D(t) - I_D = I_D \sin(\beta \tilde{s}(t)) \approx I_D \beta \tilde{s}(t) \quad \beta \ll 1. \quad (13)$$

The SNR of the electrical signal that is direct-detected by the PD in the satellite gateway becomes

$$\text{SNR}_{e,\text{pd}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|i_d(t)|^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \approx \frac{I_D^2 \beta^2}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \quad \beta \ll 1, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{shot}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{thermal}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{rin}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{beat}}(t)|^2\}, \quad (15)$$

includes the contribution of all noise sources in the optical feeder link, namely the *shot noise* sources, *thermal noise*, *Relative Intensity Noise* (RIN) of LD, and *beat noise* [?]. Note that shot noise term includes the contribution of the received optical signal, the Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noise, background optical noise and the dark current noise, whereas the beat noise term accounts the effect of combining the received optical signal with the ASE noise.

When the received optical power is between -90 and -20 dBW, it can be shown that the beat noise between received optical signal and ASE noise dominates the SNR performance of the optical feeder link [?]. In this situation,

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} \approx \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{beat}}(t)|^2\} = i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 + i_{\text{sp-sp}}^2 \approx i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 = 4 I_D I_{\text{ase}} (B_e/B_o), \quad (16)$$

where B_o is the bandwidth of the optical signal at the PD input, B_e is the bandwidth of the electrical signal at the PD output, and $I_{\text{ase}} = \mu G_{\text{o,edfa}} P_{\text{ase}}$ is the DC component generated by the ASE noise when $P_{\text{ase}} = \rho_{\text{ase}} B_o$ is the equivalent noise power of the EDFA before amplification.

Let $r(t) = s(t) + n(t)$ be the continuous-time received signal, where $n(t)$ is Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). Then, the sufficient statistics for symbol detection can be obtained after applying Match Filtering (MF) [?], *i. e.*,

$$r[n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(t) g_{\text{rx}}(t - n(1 - \delta)T_s) dt = \sum_k s[k] c[k - n] + \eta[n], \quad (17)$$

where $g_{\text{rx}}(t) = g_{\text{tx}}(-t)^*$ and, due to that,

$$c[k - n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{tx}}(t - k(1 - \delta)T_s) g_{\text{tx}}(-t + n(1 - \delta)T_s)^* dt, \quad (18)$$

$$\eta[n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} n(t) g_{\text{tx}}(-t + n(1 - \delta)T_s)^* dt, \quad (19)$$

which is the so-called Ungerboeck observation model [?]. Unfortunately, this model is not practical since the ISI in (17) is non-causal and the noise samples $\eta[n]$ are correlated. In order to avoid these problems, the signal after MF is passed through a whitening filter [?]. By doing so, we obtain

$$r'[n] = \sum_k s[k] c'[k - n] + \eta'[n], \quad (20)$$

where $c'[k]$ for $k \neq n$ is the causal time-packing ISI verifying $c'[k] * c'[-k]^* = c[k]$, and $\eta'[n]$ are AWGN samples. Note that the time-duration and magnitude of this ISI will depend on the modulation order M , the roll-off factor ρ , and overlapping factor δ selected for the time-packed transmission.

Fig. 3: Equalization process using Normalized Least Mean Squares (NLMS) algorithm.

We now focus on re-writing received signal samples in (20) in a vector-matrix form. For this, we define $\mathbf{r}' \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+L_c) \times 1}$ as the vector that stacks the received time-packed samples, *i.e.*,

$$\mathbf{r}' = \left[r' \left[\frac{(-L_c + 1)}{2} \right] \cdots r'[n] \cdots r' \left[N + \frac{(L_c - 1)}{2} \right] \right]^T, \quad (21)$$

where L_c is the number of delayed signal samples after the matched filter and N is the number of modulated symbols to be transmitted. Then, it is possible to show that

$$\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{s} + \boldsymbol{\eta}', \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+(L_c-1)/2) \times 1}$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}' \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+L_c) \times 1}$ are the vectors containing the transmitted symbols and the received noise samples, respectively, while $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+L_c) \times (N+(L_c-1)/2)}$ is the so-called convolution channel matrix that has the following structure, including the initial and final transition states:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} c'[0] & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ c'[L_c] & \cdots & c'[0] & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & c'[L_c] & \cdots & c'[0] \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & \cdots & 0 & c'[L_c] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

After explaining the key concepts behind time-packing transmission, we are now ready to study the detection strategies to recover the transmitted symbol stream.

3 Adaptive Equalization

In order to remove the interference in a multi-path channel, the optimum strategy consist on using the Maximum Likelihood Sequence Estimator (MLSE), which

can be efficiently implemented implementing the Viterbi Algorithm (VA) [?], [?]. Unfortunately, the trellis of the VA has an exponential relationship with the order of the modulation (M) that is utilized and the channel memory. This channel memory, in the case of time-packed signals, depends on the overlapping factor (δ) and the roll-off factor of the pulse-shaped SRRC filters (ρ). Thus, the larger is the overlapping factor and/or the lower the roll-off factor, the higher is the channel memory that time-packing introduces in transmission. Unfortunately, using larger overlapping degrees and lower roll-off are of high interest, since they permit to increase the throughput of the communication link. Therefore, for these cases, it is not recommended to use VA. Alternatively, we propose to use an adaptive transversal filter that performs linear equalization. By doing so, the received signal sample before performing a symbol-by-symbol detection becomes

$$\hat{s}[n] = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{y}[n], \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = [w[0] \cdots w[L_w - 1]]^T$ is the vector that stacks the L_w weights of the transversal filter, and $\mathbf{y}[n] = [r'[n - (L_w - 1)/2] \cdots r'[n] \cdots r'[n + (L_w - 1)/2]]^T$ is the vector that stacks the $(L_w - 1)/2$ a priori and posteriori received samples to the symbol to estimate. In order to determine the weights of the adaptive linear equalizer, we have resorted to the Normalized Least Mean Squares (NLMS) algorithm and a set of training symbols as illustrated in Fig. 3. Then, the updating process of the transversal filter weights for the j -th Monte-Carlo training sequence at the n -th training symbol is given by [?]

$$\mathbf{w}_j[n] = \mathbf{w}_j[n - 1] + \frac{\mu}{P_y} e_j[n] \mathbf{y}_j[n], \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_j[n] \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{w}_j[n - 1] \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$ represent the vector of L_w coefficients of the transversal filter at the current and previous training iteration, μ is the forgetting parameter of the NLMS algorithm, P_y is the power of the received samples, $e_j[n] = s_j[n] - \hat{s}_j[n]$ is the error from the current estimated symbol and the training one, which are denoted as $\hat{s}_j[n]$ and $s_j[n]$, respectively.

4 Performance Evaluation

The error correction capabilities that the MCS of the NB-IoT transmission has on the end-to-end reverse link of the GEO satellite system (*i.e.*, from the IoT device to the satellite gateway) is now evaluated. For this purpose, we first present the simulation setup and, after that, we show different different figures of merit that are relevant to characterize the end-to-end error correction performance.

4.1 Simulation setup

The NB-IoT transmitted signal corresponds to the NPUSCH format 1 when TBS = 256 bits. The corresponding simulated code rates are:

- $R_c^{\text{UL}} = 0.27, 0.44$ for BPSK (2-PAM) in the radio access (optical feeder) link.
- $R_c^{\text{UL}} = 0.17, 0.67$ for QPSK (4-PAM) in the radio access (optical feeder) link.

The BPSK (QPSK) modulation symbols that the satellite receives in uplink from the IoT terminal are first detected, and then re-modulated using 2-PAM (4-PAM) with a Square-Root Raised-Cosine (SRRC) pulse shaping filter with roll-off factor $\rho = 0.25$ and overlapping factor $\delta = 0, 25, 40\%$. The resulting time-domain signal is used to modulate in intensity the light beam of the Laser Diode onboard the satellite, using for this purpose an external Match-Zehnder Modulation (MZM) that works in its linear region. Finally, the optical signal that the satellite gateway receives in downlink is amplified, converted into an electrical signal using a PIN-diode Photodetector (Direct Detection), matched-filtered, equalized using an adaptive linear MMSE filter, and turbo decoded.

Table 8 summarizes the parameters of the optical feeder link, taking into account both the optical gains and optical losses, and the different sources of optical noise [?]. The effect of any other not listed parameter is considered negligible. According to them, the mean received optical power is

$$\begin{aligned} P_{o,\text{rx}}[\text{dBm}] &= P_{o,\text{ld}}[\text{dBm}] + G_{o,\text{tx}}[\text{dB}] + G_{o,\text{rx}}[\text{dB}] - L_{o,\text{fsl}}[\text{dB}] \\ L_{o,\text{sys}}[\text{dB}] - L_{o,\text{atm}}[\text{dB}] &= -33.4[\text{dBm}] - L_{o,\text{atm}}[\text{dB}]. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

When $L_{o,\text{atm}} = 0$ dB (clear-sky), the DC current at the PD output is $I_D = 11.43$ mA, whereas the DC current generated by the ASE noise is $I_{\text{ase}} = 0.125$ mA regardless the weather. Thus, if the intensity modulation index $\beta = 0.5$, the SNR of the electrical signal at the output of the PD becomes

$$\text{SNR}_{e,\text{pd}}[\text{dB}] = 16.75[\text{dB}] - L_{o,\text{atm}}[\text{dB}]. \quad (27)$$

The larger is the intensity modulation indexes β , the more notable becomes the non-linear distortion of the MZM. In this situation, Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) is needed to keep the impact of non-linear distortion under control [?].

The minimum and maximum tested E_b/N_0 for the access are $E_b/N_{0,\text{min}} = 0$ dB and $E_b/N_{0,\text{max}} = 11$ dB respectively, using a fixed step size of 0.1 dB. Finally, the SNR in the feeder link was set to Then, $\text{PER} = 1 - (1 - P_b)^N$, where N is the message length and P_b is the BER of BPSK/QPSK assuming an optical feeder link with excellent SNR. Regarding the normalized throughput, it is computed as

$$\text{TP} = \frac{(1 - \text{PER}) N_b R_c}{(1 + \rho)(1 - \delta)}, \quad (27)$$

where N_b is the number of bits per modulated symbol. Note that roll-off factor (ρ) of the feeder link and the code rate R_c of the NB-IoT transmission penalizes the throughput of the end-to-end link, whereas the overlapping factor (δ) and the modulation order (N_b) increase it.

The use of time-packing compensates the reduction in the data rate that error control coding schemes and finite duration SRRC pulses introduce. Moreover, the use of a suitable MCS in the end-to-end NB-IoT transmission controls the errors that are added either in the radio access and optical feeder links of the reverse

Table 8: Parameters of the optical feeder link of the HTS system.

Symbol	Optical Link Parameter	Value	Unit
$P_{o,ld}$	Optical power of LD (incl. EDFA booster)	23.0	dBm
$G_{o,tx}$	Optical gain of transmitter (satellite telescope)	114.3	dBi
$G_{o,rx}$	Optical gain of receiver (ground telescope)	125.8	dBi
$L_{o,fsl}$	FSL of optical link (1550 nm, 39000 km)	290.0	dB
$L_{o,atm}$	Atmospheric attenuation	1.7	dB
$L_{o,sys}$	System losses in the optical feeder link	6.5	dB
G_{edfa}	Gain of the optical amplifier (EDFA)	50.0	dB
μ	Responsivity of photodetector (PIN diode)	0.5	A/W
B_e	Bandwidth of electrical filter (PD output)	1.5	GHz
B_o	Bandwidth of optical channel (1550 nm)	12.5	GHz
ρ_{ase}	PSD of amplified spontaneous emissions	2.0×10^{-19}	W/Hz
ρ_{rin}	PSD of RIN process (normalized)	-160	dBc/Hz
ρ_{back}	PSD of background noise at EDFA input	7.6×10^{-25}	W/Hz
i_n	Electrical noise current spectral density	1.0×10^{-11}	A
i_{dark}	Dark current at the PIN diode output	1.0×10^{-10}	A

Table 9: Maximum throughput in the radio access and optical feeder link.

Modulation	Rc=0.27	Rc=0.44	Rc=0.17	Rc=0.67
BPSK	$\delta=0\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.216$	$\delta=0\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.352$	-	-
	$\delta=25\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.288$	$\delta=25\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.469$		
	$\delta=40\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.36$	$\delta=40\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.58$		
QPSK	-	-	$\delta=0\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.17$	$\delta=0\% \Rightarrow \gamma=1.072$
			$\delta=25\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.362$	$\delta=25\% \Rightarrow \gamma=1.4293$
			$\delta=40\% \Rightarrow \gamma=0.4533$	$\delta=40\% \Rightarrow \gamma=1.7867$

GEO satellite channel. In this regards, Table 9 shows the maximum throughput that is achievable when code rates $R_c = 0.27, 0.44$ ($R_c = 0.17, 0.67$) are used for BPSK/2-PAM (QPSK/4-PAM) modulation in the access/feeder link, with overlapping factors $\delta = 0, 25, 40\%$. This maximum throughput attains the form $\gamma = \frac{N_b R_c}{(1+\rho)(1-\delta)}$. Finally, the equalizer is based on an adaptive linear MMSE filter, as described in Section 3, with a training sequence of 100 000 symbols, $L_w = 13$ coefficients to estimate the current symbol, and a forgetting parameter $\mu = 0.05$.

4.2 Simulation Results

Fig. 4 shows the BER of the reverse link (end-to-end) in terms of the E_b/N_0 . It is composed of three sub-figures, each of them for a different overlapping factor: $\delta = 0\%$ (Fig. 4.4a), $\delta = 25\%$ (Fig. 4.4b), and $\delta = 40\%$ (Fig. 4.4c). In these figures, the modulation is not the essential parameter, but rather the code rate, as the Energy-per-Bit is kept constant for all tested schemes. Consequently, we should expect that the lower the code rate the better the BER. However, this conclusions is valid at high E_b/N_0 , since the redundancy that introduces the channel coding may increase the number of erroneous bits after its iterative

decoding process at lower values of E_b/N_0 . As a result, we are able to distinguish three regions in Fig. 4: i) low E_b/N_0 values ($E_b/N_0 \leq 5$ dB), ii) Medium E_b/N_0 values ($5 \text{ dB} \leq E_b/N_0 \leq 7.5$ dB), and iii) High E_b/N_0 values ($E_b/N_0 \geq 7.5$ dB). In the first region, the scheme with the best BER corresponds to the QPSK/4-PAM in the access/feeder link with $R_c = 1$. This means that the best option at low SNR is an uncoded transmission, since the turbo decoding process augments the number of errors when it is used at lower code rates (*i.e.*, diverges). Next, in the Medium SNR region, the MCS with $R_c = 0.27$ and $R_c = 0.44$ start to provide a better BER than the MCS with $R_c = 0.67$ (the largest one). This means that for these code rates the turbo decoded code words have a lower number of errors than the received ones. Finally, if the E_b/N_0 is larger than 7.5 dB, then the lower the code rate provides the best BER performance as it was initially expected.

Regarding the effect of the overlapping factor, we observe that the BER for time-packed BPSK provides the same performance as without using time-packing. On the contrary, for QPSK modulation and code rate $R_c = 1$ (uncoded transmission), there is a visible error floor when the SNR of the feeder link is 15 dB at overlapping factors $\delta = 25\%$ and 40% . This error floor disappears when the SNR of the feeder link increases. So, the turbo-code permits to reduce/remove the time-packed ISI that the equalizer cannot remove.

Next, Fig. 5 shows the end-to-end PER of the reverse link as function of the SNR of the access link. Similarly to the previous figure, it is formed of three-subfigures, each of them of a particular overlapping factor: Fig. 5a for $\delta = 0\%$, Fig. 5b for $\delta = 25\%$, and for Fig. 5c for $\delta = 40\%$. In this case, the distribution of the plotted curves is quite different from Fig. 4. After introducing the modulation and code rate, we obtain, that the lower code rate per bit the better the PER. In this case, it is possible to check that QPSK with $R_c = 0.17$ and BPSK with $R_c = 0.27$ provide the best BER. Next, it comes the BPSK with $R_c = 0.44$ and QPSK with $R_c = 0.67$. In both cases, PER performance with and without time-packing show similar performance results. Finally, the uncoded transmissions ($R_c = 1$) provide the worst PER. In fact, all of them (time-packed and not) show an error floor. Theoretical PER is close to the optimal one for BPSK and for QPSK follows a part of this bound. On the contrary, coded transmissions (time and no time-packed signals) do not show any error floor when the SNR of the feeder link is 15 dB. Furthermore, their performance is close to the one for SNR of the feeder link is extremely high.

Finally, Fig. 6 shows the normalized throughput in terms of the SNR for overlapping factors $\delta = 0\%$ (Fig. 6a), $\delta = 25\%$ (Fig. 6b) and $\delta = 40\%$ (Fig. 6c). When studying these figures, it is possible to divide them into three regions in terms of SNR: i) SNRs lower than 4 dB, ii) SNRs between 4 and 6 dB, and iii) SNRs larger than 6 dB. In the first region, the scheme that provides the best normalized throughput is the one using QPSK/4-PAM modulation and code rate $R_c = 0.17$. Next, in the second region, the best scheme is provided by the scheme with BPSK/2-PAM modulation and code rate $R_c = 0.27$. Finally, in the third and last region, the scheme that has the largest normalized throughput is the one that uses QPSK/4-PAM modulation with code rate $R_c = 0.67$. This

Fig. 4: End-to-end BER as a function of E_b/N_0 when $\rho = 0.25$. Modulation schemes: BPSK/2-PAM (red lines), QPSK/4-PAM (blue lines). Coded rates: $R_c = 0.27$ (solid circle markers), $R_c = 0.44$ (non-filled square markers), $R_c = 0.17$ (solid diamond markers), and $R_c = 0.67$ (non-filled triangle markers). Ideal feeder link: Black lines. An adaptive linear MMSE equalizer used in the gateway.

classification is independent of using time-packing or not. In all of them, the same distribution is observed. Note that when it is used, a larger normalized throughput is obtained without penalty on the cut-off SNR. This is because the turbo-decoder is able to remove the residual ISI-plus-noise power that the adaptive linear MMSE equalizer is not able to remove.

5 Conclusions

This paper has focused on the use of time-packing in the feeder link (downlink) of a satellite reverse link. Additionally, the downlink uses optical technology for wireless communication, instead of radio technology, to increase the point to point data rate of the feeder link. Performance evaluation has been carried out using the BER, PER and Throughput of NPUSCH format 1 of NB-IoT, which uses either BPSK or QPSK modulations. The NB-IoT standard has been modeled in the access link (uplink) of the reverse satellite link. Towards this regard, it

Fig. 5: End-to-end PER as a function of SNR when $\rho = 0.25$. Modulation schemes: BPSK/2-PAM (red lines), QPSK/4-PAM (blue lines). Overlapping factors: $\delta = 0$ (continuous lines), $\delta = 0.25$ (dashed lines), and $\delta = 0.4$ (dash-dotted lines). Coded rates: $R_c = 0.27$ (solid circle markers), $R_c = 0.44$ (non-filled square markers), $R_c = 0.17$ (solid diamond markers), and $R_c = 0.67$ (non-filled triangle markers). Ideal feeder link: Black lines. Adaptive MMSE equalizer.

has been detailed in the system model how to compute the NB-IoT code rates for the NPUSCH channel for BPSK/QPSK modulation when the transport block size is kept constant to $TBS = 256$ bits. The satellite only conducts a symbol-by-symbol detection and re-modulation process, time-packing processing, electrical-to-optical conversion, and downlink transmission to the satellite gateway. There, it has been used an adaptive-MMSE equalizer to remove the ISI that introduces the time-packed modulation. Results show that this equalizer is able to remove notable part of the ISI, but some residual ISI remains. The lower the SNR of the feeder link, $SNR_{e,pd}$ and the higher is the modulation order, the lower the performance of the adaptive-equalizer. Uncoded BPSK transmissions do not present any error floor at practical SNR values of the feeder link ($SNR_{e,pd} = 15$ dB) and medium-large overlapping factors ($\delta = 25$ and 40%). However, this is not the case for uncoded QPSK-4-PAM modulation which presents an error floor. To remove this residual ISI, it has been taken advantage of the turbo-encoding

(a) Normalized Throughput for $\delta = 0\%$ (b) Normalized Throughput for $\delta = 25\%$

(c) Normalized Throughput for $\delta = 40\%$

Fig. 6: End-to-End Normalized Throughput as a function of E_b/N_0 when the roll-off factor is $\rho = 0.25$. Modulation schemes: BPSK-2-PAM (red lines), QPSK-4-PAM (blue lines). Overlapping factors: $\delta = 0$ (continuous lines), $\delta = 0.25$ (dashed lines), and $\delta = 0.4$ (dash-dotted lines). Coded rates: for BPSK-2-PAM $R_c=0.27$ (solid circle markers), $R_c=0.44$ (non-filled square markers), for QPSK-4-PAM $R_c=0.17$ (solid diamond markers), and $R_c=0.67$ (non-filled triangle markers). Equalizer used in detection: adaptive MMSE.

process of NB-IoT frames. Results show that it is able to remove the residual ISI after the equalization process even for actual values of SNR in the feeder link and large overlapping factors. Consequently, it is possible to claim that wireless optical links assisted by time-packed waveforms could be an interesting solution for extending the traffic capacity of the next 5G+, and beyond integrated terrestrial-satellite networks. Specially, when they have to provide service to IoT devices, whose traffic demand is forecast to increase in the following years.